

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSISTANCE IN ADJUSTING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO SCHOOL

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Abstract. For a primary school student, a school trip can be exciting and surprising, and it can be a new experience for them. Parents and caregivers should strive to make the transition as smooth as possible. Psychological support can be especially helpful when dealing with a new environment, teachers, and peers. Support can help reduce anxiety, improve academic performance and develop social skills. This article focuses on the study of methods of providing psychological support to elementary school students in adapting to school.

Keywords: depression, stress, group therapy, active listening, individuality.

INTRODUCTION

Adjusting to primary school can be a difficult time for students, and psychological support can help them cope with the change. Psychological support is associated with improved academic achievement and mental health. Research has shown that children with mental health problems learn and retain information (Vahedi et al., 2019). Children experiencing depression, anxiety, or stress may also be at risk of developing delinquent behavior. This is why psychological support is so important in ensuring that children learn and grow in a safe and supportive environment.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the system of compulsory one-year preparation of children for primary education" Resolution No. 132 of March 9, 2020 with amendments and additions on input

Accelerate the coverage of children in the remote areas of the republic with preschool education, raise healthy, active, well-rounded, socially adapted children, create conditions for successful educational activities in the future, and provide plans for quality preparation for primary education. 'tilde.[lex.uz]

RESULTS

Psychological support is necessary when dealing with elementary school students, educators and teachers should create a safe and supportive environment for children. And of course the following methods can be used:

1. Active Listening. Active listening is an important skill that helps parents and teachers understand the emotional and psychological problems of students. Active listening involves making eye contact, paying attention, and reflecting on what the child is saying. A teacher or tutor can be attentive and sensitive and create a safe space for a student to communicate their difficulties.

2. Encouragement and positive reinforcement. Encouragement and positive reinforcement go a long way in building elementary students' confidence. Teachers, caregivers, and parents should offer positive feedback when children are doing well academically or socially. This approach helps students develop a positive self-image and, in turn, feel comfortable in the school environment.

3. Social support. Social support is very important in school adjustment for elementary school students. Parents, caregivers, and school staff should encourage social activities such as playtime, sports, and group activities. These activities help children build friendships, develop social skills and build self-confidence.

4. Consulting Services. Counseling services can be a great option for children who are experiencing emotional or psychological difficulties. Counseling services offer a confidential and supportive environment where children can express their fears, frustrations and concerns. Counselors can help children develop coping strategies and give them tools to manage their emotions.

5. Group Therapy. Group therapy is another effective way to provide psychological support to elementary school students. Group therapy sessions can focus on specific topics such as anxiety, bullying or stress. Children can share their experiences and learn from each other. In addition, these activities help children develop social skills and make new friendships.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Adaptation of primary school students to school is a process that requires special attention and care of teachers, parents and psychologists. This period is an important stage in a child's life, because most of them are faced with daily activities, new rules of behavior and the need to communicate with new people for the first time.

Psychological support of primary school students' adaptation to school includes a number of activities that help the child to overcome emotional and psychological difficulties that arise in the process of adaptation. Here are some of these activities:

Individual interviews with a psychologist.

At the beginning of the school year, a psychologist can conduct individual interviews with each elementary school student. During these conversations, the psychologist can determine what emotions the child is experiencing, how he reacts to a new situation, and what difficulties he faces. As a result of such conversations, the psychologist can give the child the necessary advice and help him adapt to the new school.

Group lessons on the development of social skills

The ability to socialize and communicate with other people is very important for elementary school students. To help a child develop these skills, a psychologist can conduct group activities where children learn to communicate, listen to each other, and resolve conflicts.

CONCLUSIONS

Adapting to primary school can be a difficult process, and students need psychological support to adapt to the new environment. Parents, caregivers, and teachers must work together to provide a safe and comfortable environment for children. Active listening, positive reinforcement, social support, counseling services, and group therapy are effective methods of providing psychological support. By providing emotional and psychological support, children can grow and develop in a safe, supportive environment and succeed in their academic and personal lives.

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